

Limit of detection (LOD) in nonlinear concentration-response curves, with application in in-vitro mutagenicity assays

Ludwig A. Hothorn,

Im Grund 12, D-31867 Lauenau, Germany (e-mail:ludwig@hothorn.de)

(retired from Leibniz University Hannover)

Dimitrios Spiliotopoulos,

Xenometrix AG, CH-4123 Allschwil, Switzerland

Maricel Marin-Kuan,

Societe des Produits Nestle, CH-1000 Lausanne 26, Switzerland

Christian Ritz,

National Institute of Public Health (Statens Institut for Folkesundhed)

DK-1455 Kobenhavn, Denmark

August 27, 2021

Abstract

Different-shaped nonlinear concentration-response curves of various in-vitro assays can be compared by their limit of detection (LOD). To estimate an effective dose (as LOD), a nonlinear model fit and the intercept of its prediction limit with concentration 0 is used. This represents an extension of the common calibration curve LOD estimation for strict linear concentration-response curves, conditionally after suitable transformation.

1 Introduction

In analytical biochemistry, the limit of detection (LOD) is a widespread used parameter to characterize precision of a concentration-response based method. Unfortunately, several definitions for LOD exist [3]. Here we focus the specific LOD definition of a minimum detectable value (MDV) [5] based on the weighted calibration method [4] related to the guidance in the IUPAC orange book, DIN 32645 and ISO 11843. This model assumes a linear (e.g. after transformation) concentration-response curve with several concentration values (replicated or even un-replicated). The intersection of the upper prediction limit from a simple linear regression model with a particular value, here the value of zero concentration (according to DIN32645), is used for an inverse calibration approach to estimate the related concentration.

The in-vitro mutagenicity experiments are specific. The zero concentration is experimental, i.e. the solvent control. The shape of the curves are highly non-linear and quite different for different assays. Moreover, the curves may be non-monotonic, since downturn effects at high concentrations are possible. Different assays with different conditions, e.g. different bacteria strains, different type of metabolization use different concentration ranges. Therefore, the MDV, a concentration commonly between 0 and C_{low} seems to be an appropriate measure to compare the detection sensitivity of quite different assays.

Here, the linear approach is extended to nonlinear models: i) fitting a flexible 5-parametric log-logistic

model [6], ii) estimation its upper prediction limit, iii) intersection with 0 as absolute threshold λ , iv) inverse regression estimation of EC_λ . This method is shown in detail in chapter 3 by means of a data example with explicit R-code.

Notice, model averaging over several pre-specified models [7] can be a robust alternative to the use of just the 5PL model.

2 An example: Comparing two Ames assay variants

The Ames assay is a widespread-used in-vitro mutagenicity assay where several variants are available now [8]. In Figure 1, the concentration-response curves of a new nano assay and an established micro assay are compared for the E-coli bacteria strain with metabolic activation (left panel .. box plots, right panel ... 5 PL model fits with mean values): Both nano and micro assay reveal an Ames positive response,

Figure 1: Example for concentration-response curves: nano vs. micro Ames assay

i.e. a significant increase of at least one concentration vs. solvent control by Dunnett test [2] whereas an at least three-fold increase vs. control occurred. However, the experimental concentrations in the nano assay are much smaller than in the micro assay. Because both curves contain the zero-concentration solvent control, their sensitivities can be compared by means of their LOD's.

3 An algorithm for LOD estimation of different-shaped nonlinear concentration-response curves

The CRAN package *library(drc)* contains functionality for 1) nonlinear model fit, 2) estimation of its prediction interval and 3) inverse regression for effective dose EC_λ estimation [6]:

```
library(drc)
mod1Nano<-drm(Trans~Conc, data=ExampleNano, fct=LL.5()) # 1): 5PL model fit
PINano<-predict(mod1Nano, data.frame(Conc=0), interval = "prediction")[3] # 2): prediction interval
LODNano<-ED(mod1Nano, PINano, interval = "delta", type="absolute") # 3): ED for absolute threshold
```

The LOD for the micro assay is 16.1 and for the nano assay is 0.63, i.e. the Nano assay reveals the same global outcome of Ames-positive, but its LOD is only 3.9% of the micro assay.

With variance heterogeneous data one should act cautiously, e.g. using a suitable transformation.

3.1 LOD estimation when a downturn effect at high concentration is possible

Overdosing is common in in-vitro mutagenicity assay to avoid false negative outcomes. Therefore, a downturn effect at high concentration is possible. One could empirically simply eliminate those concentrations from the LOD modeling after effect reversal. Better seems to be the use of a model, which was formulated exactly for non-monotonies, e.g. the CRS model [1] here in an example with a serious downturn effect:

Figure 2: Example data with a serious downturn effect at high concentration

```
micam.CRS.5c <- drm(Trans ~ Conc, data = DI98pAfBM, fct = CRS.5c())
PREDmicam <- predict(micam.CRS.5c, data.frame(Conc=0.0001), interval = "prediction")[3]
LODmicam <- ED(micam.CRS.5c, PREDmicam, interval = "delta", type="absolute")
```

The LOD using the CRS-model is 96.2, whereas using the monotonic 5PL-model LOD can not be estimated.

4 Summary

Different-shaped nonlinear concentration-response curves of various in-vitro assay variants can be compared by their LOD's. As an extension to the common LOD for linear calibration curves, here a nonlinear model fit with its prediction interval is proposed, where the intersection of the upper prediction limit with the concentration of zero λ is used to estimate its effective dose. By means of the *library(drc)* these complex calculations can be easily performed.

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